

Political Representation of Public Sector Employees

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Summary

- We examine the political representation of public sector employees – passively in terms of voting and standing for election, as well as actively in terms of influencing public policies after obtaining political office.
 - We study these issues using population-wide individual-level register data from Norway covering the 2003-2019 period.
 - We find that public sector employees display one to five percentage points higher turnout in elections, particularly when working in their residential municipality.
 - We show that public sector employees are strongly overrepresented on election lists and in local elected offices, which is driven predominantly by their self-selection into standing for elected office rather than demand-side effects from party and voter selection.
 - We uncover at best limited evidence that the political (over)representation of public sector employees affects the levels of public spending, employment and wages – which offers little support for long-lasting concerns about budget (and bureau) maximizing bureaucrats.
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1. Introduction

A long-standing academic debate relates to whether (or not) public employees differ fundamentally from private-sector workers in terms of their political beliefs and actions. Such a difference may arise because most citizens only consume public services, while public employees are producers as well as consumers of public services. This ‘double motive’ may heighten the incentives of public employees to become politically active. As a result, they would be expected to show up at the polls in larger numbers, be more likely to put themselves forward for election to public office, and exert more effort to influence the direction and implementation of public policies (e.g., Tullock 1965; Dunleavy 1991; Garand et al. 1991; Yackee 2023).

Empirical evidence for these predictions has remained incomplete and unpersuasive in part due to the absence of detailed longitudinal individual-level data as well as critical concerns posed by preference-based job selection (i.e. the likelihood that individuals with certain characteristics self-select into becoming public sector employees). Nevertheless, understanding the drivers and implications of the political representation of public sector employees is of substantive importance from a democratic perspective since public sector employees play a fundamental – and often increasing – role in the governing of modern societies (Putnam 1973; Huber 2000; Orren and Skowronek 2017).

In a series of recent studies, we have therefore engaged with these questions using a novel and unique combination of four main data sources. These include population-wide individual-level register data from Norway covering the 2003-2019 period, detailed information about election results at the Norwegian local government level, responses

to survey questionnaires obtained from a large cross-section of local councilors, and municipality-level statistics on local public expenditures, employment and wages.

2. Research questions and main findings

Using a range of empirical approaches, we exploit these data sources to address three main questions. The first question is: *Does working in the public sector rather than the private sector have a causal effect on electoral participation?* In other words, are individuals working in the public sector more likely to turn out and cast a vote on Election Day? This would be expected if the ‘double motive’ mentioned above heightens the incentives of public sector employees to become politically active. To answer this question, we track the electoral participation of the *same* individuals over time during a) shifts between private and public sector employment, b) relocations between Norwegian municipalities, and c) shifts from employment into retirement. For the first of these changes, the expectation is that a move from the private to the public sector increases an individual’s incentive to turn out and vote (even when assuming that ideological and other preferences are fixed in the short term). The second change exploits that only public employees working inside their residential municipality act as a producer of their own local public services, which would increase their motivation to turn out and vote (Moe 2006). Finally, retirement eliminates an individual’s role and incentive as a producer of public services, which thus naturally also removes any additional motivation to turn out and vote.

Consistent across all three identification strategies, our main findings indicate that local **public sector employees display one to five percentage points higher turnout in**

elections. These effects arise particularly when public sector employees are employed in their residential municipality, and largely dissipate upon retirement. The latter finding echoes findings from the Norwegian Election Studies. Rattsø and Sørensen (2016) indeed demonstrate not only a strong sectoral divergence in voters' party preferences, but also show that ideological positions between public and private-sector workers diverge during working age before converging again after retirement.

Taken together, these patterns confirm that local public employees' double motive as producers and consumers of public services induces them to turn out at higher rates during elections. Even so, we should note that the size of this effect is found to be substantially smaller than is commonly suggested by extant cross-sectional evidence.

Having established that public sector employees are more likely to vote during elections than those working in the private sector (or those not working), we turn our attention to another form of political participation – namely, standing for election. We thereby investigate two closely related elements linked to the following research question: *What are nature and drivers of public employees' electoral representation?* On the one hand, we study whether the 'double motive' of public sector employees to become politically active (see above) makes that they become over-represented on election lists and among elected representatives. On the other hand, we take a similar approach to the turnout study mentioned above, and evaluate whether changing employment from the private to the public sector (or vice versa) or shifting job location from inside to outside one's residential municipality (or vice versa) affects individuals' self-selection into politics by

adding (or removing) an additional 'motive' to stand for election.

Our main findings indicate that **public sector employees are politically over-represented at the local government level (relative to their share in the local population)**. Furthermore, public employees are found to have a higher probability of election conditional on standing for election, since their over-representation is larger among elected council members compared to election candidates (see Figure A.1 below). We show that these effects are mostly driven by individuals' self-selection into politics rather than voter or party selection strategies in favor of public sector employees. For instance, we find that individuals become more likely to become politically active when they take up a public sector job, or when public employees change work location from outside to inside their home municipality (which increases their 'personal stakes' in local election outcomes; Moe 2006; West 2012).

Finally, when public sector employees are allowed to hold elected office during their employment and become heavily over-represented in such positions (see above), one might worry that there could arise substantial conflicts of interest on the part of elected public sector employees. That is, if public sector employees are "self-interested political actors who desire to increase government spending for their own well-being" (Cigler 1990, p. 638), their political representation may tempt them to sway public policies towards their professional interests. This would be expected to translate into increased public spending, employment and wages (e.g., Tullock 1965; Dunleavy 1991; Garand et al. 1991; Yackee 2023), and leads to our third main research question: *What – if any – are the (direct and indirect) substantive effects of civil servants' passive representation in politics?*

Overall, our findings provide very little support for the rather pessimistic perspective on the political representation of public sector employees expressed above. That is, we show that **public sector employees differ little from other members within their party in terms of ideology and policy preferences**. Although they appear to move their party slightly towards the left of the political spectrum, increasing the level of **political representation of public sector employees has no significant impact on the levels of public sector spending, employment and wages at the municipal level**. It is not obvious to pinpoint the exact reason for this null finding with the data at our disposal. Hence, future research should investigate to what extent public sector employees on average may simply care more about the common good than their own self-interest, or face high levels of party discipline restricting their room for maneuver within the party.

3. Policy recommendations

Given their ‘double motive’ as producers and consumers of public services, should public sector employees be allowed to stand for election and enter elected assemblies during their employment? Fundamental disagreement on this issue is reflected in widely diverging institutional frameworks around the world. Some countries – including the US and UK – impose strict statutory limitations, whereas other countries – including Norway and Spain – have very permissive rules (Brændle and Stutzer 2016). Although our findings naturally relate to one country with a particular set of institutional characteristics, our analysis nonetheless may offer some insights for the design of institutional arrangements that deal with public employees’ (in)eligibility for political office.

First, **eligibility restrictions are most pressing when public sector employees display diverging policy preferences** (e.g., relative to other members of the same political party), because increased descriptive representation then may induce concerns about a concomitant shift in public policies. Since we find no evidence of such within-party differences in policy preferences, this undermines support for imposing blanket restrictions on the eligibility of public sector employees for political office (at least in our Norwegian setting).

Second, **institutional arrangements on the (in)eligibility of public employees for political office should only target those most able to influence their own job security and work conditions**. This is likely to occur only under very specific conditions, such as those who work and live (and vote) in the same jurisdiction. The representation of central or county government employees on municipal councils – or even municipal public employees working outside their residential municipality – is likely to pose less of a problem according to our findings, which limits the need for regulations or restrictions.

Finally, our empirical evidence is limited to overall spending, employment and wage levels. As such, we cannot exclude the possibility of conflicts of interest arising linked to sectorial affiliation (e.g., teachers biased towards higher education spending) or in other policy outcomes (e.g., use of competitive tendering, cost efficiency). **Policy-makers should carefully consider a broad range of outcome indicators before imposing targeted restrictions – or a blanket ban – on public employees holding elected office.**

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

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Further Information:

- Geys, Benny and Rune Jørgen Sørensen (2022). Public Sector Employment and Voter Turnout. *American Political Science Review* 116(1): 367-373.
- Geys, Benny, Zuzana Murdoch and Rune Jørgen Sørensen (2022). The Political (Over)Representation of Public Sector Employees. *Journal of Public Administration Research and Theory* 32(2): 326-341.
- Geys, Benny, Zuzana Murdoch and Rune Jørgen Sørensen (2023). Public Employees as Elected Politicians: Assessing the Substantive Effects of Passive Representation. *Journal of Politics*, forthcoming.

Figures:

Figure A.1. Public sector employee representation in local politics (2007-2019)

Notes. The vertical axes measure the share of public sector employees among council representatives (triangles) and on election lists (circles), while the horizontal axis indicates the share public sector employees in local electorates. The left diagram covers elections to the county council and the right diagram shows data for municipal councils. The lines reflect situations where the share of public sector employees in the electorate corresponds to its share on election lists and among council members. The plots are based on data for the municipal and county council elections in 2007, 2011, 2015 and 2019.

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